

ARCHETYPAL REPRESENTATIONS ABOUT INDIGENOUS PEOPLE ABOUT THE BRAZILIAN COLLECTIVE UNCONSCIOUS

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13958761

Geovane Leonardo dos Santos Braga

Pedagogue. Teacher in the Public School System of the State of Espírito Santo. Psychology student. Master in Communication and Education. E-mail: geovaneleonardopsicologo@hotmail.com.

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Pedagogue. Psychoanalyst. Post-Doctorate in Psychology. E-mail: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the theme of the formation of the archetype and its relationship to the Brazilian Indian, using as a mechanism of adaptation an archetypal model already consolidated in the popular imagination, namely Adam and Eve and their short existence in the Garden of Paradise, in which the comparison becomes a target of indignation when it is assumed that the two characters were expelled from their land because of a crime and the Brazilian natives are expelled because of the greed of the white man. Thus, this archetype of a good individual, but wronged, gains strength through the literature that claims to be specialized. This is a bibliographical essay. Traditionally, an archetype does not intend to represent a bizarre objective about some target object and, if this happens in the case of the indigenous people, it is precisely because Brazil, after centuries, is still a European colony, enslaved by the pathetic sense of believing that it is a representation of the old world and, under a spirit of overprotection of its native peoples, in which the opulence of laws aimed at the full protection of someone so harmless disguises its true intentions of keeping them as something rare, a symbol of the virtuousness of the land, creating a contrast with the people who originated from the mixture of others, as if the admission that they were all natural Brazilians represented a cause for disturbance, violating the natural right of the indigenous people and provoking divine wrath because of the hybridization that all Brazilian people represent; Thus, reality is denied, adopting an extra semantic condition, in which the native remains pure and the European does not recognize himself as contaminated through consanguineous crossing. The interpretation that is projected onto the psychology of the object, in this case, is controversial in itself, because it is based on information that is produced and disseminated for ideological purposes of maintaining a vision created many centuries ago, as if the full impact of technological development and national thought could not affect indigenous people. Social indignation is evident when Brazilian aborigines present themselves using modern cars and communication devices, using machines for planting and harvesting, as if they were obliged to persist in their traditional methods.

Keywords: Indigenous. Archetype. Jungian Psychology. Social constructs.

INTRODUCTION

Archetypes can be understood as primordial forms that serve as a matrix for human experiences and behaviors and, most interestingly, such elements are sociological constructions disseminated, not through the collective unconscious, but through doctrines and other elements that blend into life, subtle and uncompromising way. They are symbols that represent a variety of things, such as feelings, situations, behaviors; it is up to each culture, in particular, to define its meaning of being and being able to express the target object of each society.

In Brazil, the first archetypal representation of the natives was that they were savages, but docile and immaculate creatures, incapable of practicing any type of evil and/or violence, or even committing any capital sin. This sophisticated construction was inserted into textbooks, legends, liturgies and plays, literature as an unquestionable and indomitable truth and, nowadays, every time the television shows a report on the indigenous people, what is presented about them is a caricature of kindness and clemency.

This archetype that was created about the indigenous people became so powerful and, here, a space opens up to explain the redundancy, that all of it is, in itself, powerful; but, the issue portrayed is about the conscious and deliberate construction of a surreal image about an object and that, even with all the scientific apparatus available, it remains strong and insurmountable, leading even individuals with solid training at academic levels to persist in the belief of this construct.

This paradoxical archetypal idealization of the Brazilian aborigines had a conflicting interest between the dizzying Europe, which wanted the new world to be built in its image and divine identity, and the Kingdom of Algarves, which needed labor to be able to exploit the Colony. The first group advocated the extermination of all natives, so that a new Europe could be built there; however, the lack of individuals of blood to carry out such an undertaking as the one they intended to undertake forced the creation of a condition so that the genocide could not be justified by the simple megalomaniacal interest of Europe, as occurred in other regions of Latin America.

When the Portuguese Crown discovered, to its distress, that the Brazilian natives were not fit for the work that depended on them and that the development of the colony required, it decided to destroy them all, without exception. In this, the Catholic Church found an opportunity to establish itself through useless work, but which could save its shady ideals from persecution by the European nobility. This was followed by bloody debates between individuals who argued that the Indians were bestial creatures and that their extermination would not make

the slightest difference in the evolution of the world, and, on the other hand, defenders of them appeared, claiming that they were peaceful and pure-spirited creatures, almost angelic; both categories making arguments based on reports from sailors, that is, neither party had experienced any type of empirical contact with the natives of *Tierra Brasilis*.

This simply makes it clear that both defenders and accusers created archetypes about an object of which they had no real notion of its representation. When the priests of the Society of Jesus took on the campaign to catechize the indigenous people, they adopted the ideal represented by a very peaceful character for their discourse; however, their behavior revealed that they had adopted the image of a primitive beast, who spoke a strange and impious language; therefore, they should be subjugated by another beautiful and erudite one, in the same way that their behavior should be modified to the point of adapting to the European Christian ideal.

Behind the idealism of safeguarding the spiritual purity of the indigenous people was the Holy See's thirst for power, which could grow in an inhospitable environment from a political point of view. To hide its intentions, it took care to give meaning to its purposes, because the results were the most ridiculous possible, since it was unable to convert the natives to the Christian faith. They baptized them, but that meant very little or nothing to them. The letters sent to the bishop stated that the Indians were kind and pure creatures, representing God's most sublime creation and, if it were not for their pagan faith, they would be perfect.

With this demagogic discourse, they dehumanized the Brazilian Indians, precisely because no human being is peaceful and receptive to what they do not know. From then on, historians and history books have repeated this absurd invention, producing and reproducing an idealized image of a being who surrenders, without any kind of phenomenological resistance, to the destruction of his belief, to its replacement by another, completely unknown and without any causal connection with his culture, which, in fact, was destroyed [*almost*] completely.

The next step was to prevent the Indians from telling their story, turning them into legally incapable individuals, equating them with idiots (individuals with an IQ of less than 40), because this would make their speech seem childish and worthless. Therefore, they would have to elect someone to speak for them and, within this wonderful and perfect process, the construction of the archetypal symbol about the figure to be imagined, by the population, about the Brazilian Indian would obtain maximum success.

THE ARCHETYPAL SYMBOL BUILT ON THE BRAZILIAN INDIAN

History tells that the Indians were peaceful when the Portuguese arrived in Brazilian

lands and that there was even a very friendly relationship; which proves an idyllic construction and, at the same time, a bucolic construction of the native's life in the middle of the dense jungle, as if he were the representation of Adam and Eve, in the Hebrew mythological Garden of Eden and this condition was transformed into an archetype that took over the popular imagination of Brazilians, in general. Hillman (1992, p. 22) explains that, "archetypes are basic and universal structures of the psyche, the formal patterns of their modes of relationship are archetypal patterns"; logically, in order to create the archetype about the indigenous people of *Tierra Brasilis*, they needed something that was already, in a certain way, universalized, through a constructed and internalized symbolic image.

Let it be clear that the simple fact that history thus portrays the first reaction of the indigenous people to the potential colonizers already takes away from them all human essence, placing them in a universe that is not linked to either man or animal; since both species do not show themselves to be indolent in the presence of something that is new, understanding by the term, completely unknown to them. This is a phenomenological condition that is impossible to accept, from a logical point of view, because the primitive human survival instinct demands a condition of reactive actions very different from those reported in history books and portrayed in paintings that have become classics and that are treated as true mediumistic revelations of events for which there are no reliable accounts.

This already makes it clear that the archetypal image formed about the indigenous figure is nothing more than a caricature imagined and disseminated with dubious ends to serve the private interests of groups that were trying, in some way, to obtain advantages over the territory and needed some kind of subsidy. Even after many centuries it is not possible to break with this stigma, since this is what has become for Brazilian natives, where they are silenced and excluded from Brazilian social life, except when their presence and image represent the interests of some political group; always remaining to the same extent that only one or another breaks the sacred space and stands out in the media, presenting the rehearsed speech that everyone already knows beforehand.

These rare individuals who are removed from the image bubble and who end up being exposed as exotic figures in various public places are not capable of changing the paradigm that has transformed an entire group of individuals, in which not only their natural rights have been kidnapped, but also the right to express themselves as individuals who belong to a certain species, the human species. The way indigenous people are treated, even today, makes them nothing more than non-human creatures, alien beings who inhabited this space of land when the Europeans arrived.

Traditionally, an archetype does not intend to represent a bizarre objective about some target object and, if this happens in the case of the indigenous people, it is precisely because Brazil, after centuries, is still a European colony, enslaved by the pathetic sense of believing that it is a representation of the old world and, under a spirit of overprotection of its native peoples, in which the opulence of laws aimed at the full protection of someone so harmless disguises its true intentions of keeping them as something rare, a symbol of the virtuousness of the land, creating a contrast with the people who originated from the mixture of others, as if the admission that they were all natural Brazilians represented a cause for disturbance, violating the natural right of the indigenous people and provoking divine wrath because of the hybridization that all Brazilian people represent; thus, reality is denied, adopting an extra semantic condition, in which the native remains pure and the European does not recognize himself as contaminated through consanguineous crossing.

Along the same lines, those who are descendants of indigenous people, because of the affective-loving relationships between the different peoples, cannot call themselves as such, since they are hybrids, the product of an arrogance against nature, in which two distinct species cannot unite in the name of love and affective attraction. The archetype of the pure individual must remain as a symbol of the nation, which is nothing more than a way of hiding the European feeling of aversion to all other peoples who did not belong to this caste created with who knows what intentions.

The simple fact that Europeans do not have a known origin, through an identifiable family tree, already demonstrates their interest in creating an archetype of themselves as a people that cannot be defined by elementary origins, remaining as those who are *European*, nothing more than this, nothing less than this, and the same principle was applied to the colonies that they dominated, around the world. And, the most interesting thing is that the maintenance of this *status quo* is part of the identity project of the Brazilian people, who take it as a condition of respect for the natives. For this reason, the archetype of the Brazilian indigenous, represented as docile, calm, passive, bucolic, pure, immaculate, wild, but good, is accepted by the social imaginary as a representative construction of absolute reality.

Serbena (2010) will say about the archetypes that,

This dynamism occurs through the repetition and redundancy of the experience of the symbol and its expression. Since its meaning is inexhaustible and cannot be represented in a logical way, the clarification and construction of the meaning or significance of the symbol occur through circulation around a center, with redundancy and repetitions that are increasingly closer and loaded with meaning, comparable to a spiral movement (p. 79).

Each time the history of the indigenous people is told, the archetypal stigma representing a people who were expelled from their God-given paradise is deepened. In other words, they are more subjectively linked to the two epic characters of the Bible, with the difference that the first are guilty and the second are innocent, which gives rise to indignation against those who abuse their power against them. In this way, “the set of all symbols on a theme illuminates a symbol, one through the other” (Durand, 1998, p. 17).

Under this aspect of the redemption of the white man, another indelible archetype that has been taking over the population, in the name of an unexplained and misunderstood religious feeling, but which many ill-intentioned individuals have known how to exploit with extreme sagacity, causing everyone to suffer from an amplified social evil of guilt for a crime they did not commit; however, as it is a crime that was committed by the State, all citizens must be held responsible and, in the wake of this, be punished with the *pathos* of a neurotic guilt complex.

Every time the demarcation of lands for indigenous people is discussed, there is no discussion, to the same extent, about better living conditions for these Brazilian citizens, recognized as such, since the promulgation of the Federal Constitution of 1988; however, this archetype has not yet permeated the thinking of Brazilian society, which continues to treat them as incapable, in the legal sense, in which they cannot speak for themselves, always dependent on third parties who reveal their interests (sic).

Paradoxically, when referring to Brazilian indigenous people, a whole set of symbols only serves to obscure others, such as, for example, the empirical nature of the knowledge they have about the pathogenic agents that have affected them since time immemorial, in which this entire epistemic set, transferred from parents to children, is not considered, causing them to receive vaccines and medicines created by conventional pharmaceutical industries, treating them as if they were normal human beings, contaminated by the very diseases that humanity created through its decrepit eating and health habits.

It is important to consider that the Brazilian indigenous people have been here for so long that it is not known exactly how far back they were when Pedro Álvares Cabral and his ragtag squadron arrived. And if they managed to survive and develop as a civilization without the help of any white man and all his science and knowledge, why would they depend on him today? The answer to this would be that they have weakened in the face of their own existence, making this dependence something necessary and, in a certain way, inevitable, for their survival. But to what extent?

These are questions that are not asked and, to the same extent, cannot be answered,

because this would leave the Brazilian natives in the same condition as the Europeans, namely, where did they come from? How did they appear or how did they arrive on the American continent? If the Brazilian government is as interested in the indigenous people as it likes to say, it should carry out more in-depth archaeological and anthropological studies in order to clarify their origin; which is not happening and, the way everything is presented, it is assumed that they were born spontaneously from the earth and proliferated.

In the wake of this, it follows that all their cathected libidinal energy comes from their magical thinking, not from a careful education, as if Platonism explained everything and a mysterious and hidden force had endowed them, since the womb, with this power, inoculating them with strength and vigor through the beyond. But, at the same time, this invisible and unknown being turned them into eunuchs even before they were born, because they are all docile and immaculate creatures, where even their aggressive posture is a harmful product resulting from the forced coexistence with the white man who, paradoxically, is a European who was once a pure and immaculate being like the Brazilian native; however, his contact with civilized man and his society corrupted by greed and hatred, led him to become evil and hateful. Therefore, the real and uncompromising struggle of the Brazilian is to preserve the natural purity of the indigenous people.

But here is a turning point that is a true paradox: how can one preserve one's natural purity if the one who intends to promote it is a corrupt beast? If the myth of the good savage were a theory that could be trusted, and the theory that contact with society represented the element that holds the power to destroy this sublime condition of the indigenous people, it would be enough for the whites and the state and para-state agencies to abandon them to their own fate and, in a short time, they would be back to their respective primitive pre-Cabral states. And this would be nothing more than a hypothesis, because who would report the transformation of the perverted savage into a redeemed savage, returning to the state of a natural eunuch? Therefore, the idea that Juan Rosseau plagiarized from the Chinese is shown to be just another fallacy for which there is no known condition of effective proof, devoid of the slightest condition of refutability.

Every living being is marked by a charge of desire and virility, regardless of their biological sex, which determines their libido, their will to overcome the challenges of existence and life itself. This is inherent to the act of existing, surviving and competing, having this word in its etymological and semantic sense, which is to seek together with, to ask together with, not to try to be better than the other at all times; which leads to an understanding that the human being is marked by the desire to be recognized for his merits.

Serbena (2010) argues that,

Jung expanded the concept of libido, which became a general psychic energy and not just a sexual one, as Freud conceptualized it; the view of the psyche and the unconscious changed, as it was no longer a 'blank page' at birth and the unconscious expanded to include a layer made up of structures and images common to all humanity (the archetypes) that manifested themselves in dreams, myths, religions and fairy tales. Due to this, the method of analyzing individual cases changed, including comparisons of dreams and fantasies with elements of universal mythology, in addition to personal associations (The emphasis is in the original).

At a certain point in his life, and in an attempt to explain facts that manifested themselves in similar ways in different cultures around the world, Jung ventured into the field of Anthropology and, to his surprise, what he assumed to be true actually turned out to be true. Common dreams, common thoughts, common myths even among people who had never had any kind of contact with the so-called civilized peoples, which allowed him to produce the theory of the collective unconscious and, within this scope, the idea of archetypes, which are different symbols that people use to explain or even to categorize their beliefs, creating models that fit their ways of thinking and objectifying reality, previously limited only to the subjective condition.

With regard to the Brazilian indigenous people, an entire concept was constructed, *a priori*, through fervent debates in Europe, in which the debaters on both sides knew nothing about the objective and subjective cultures of the peoples from overseas; therefore, there are two distinct interests immediately at stake, and it is up to history to report that the litigating parties were defending opposing points of view. This may well be the case; but the cruel reality is that they were talking about an object about which they could not make any objective statement, because it was unknown, and the information that reached Europe came from superstitious, hungry, dying sailors with their imaginations attacked by the lack of vitamins and minerals, relying only on their decrepit mnemonic conditions.

When they saw indigenous religious ceremonies being held, they didn't understand anything, especially because, in addition to not understanding the culture, which was completely different from that practiced in Europe, torturing, burning and killing individuals in public squares, it was natural that the priests judged the natives from the European otherworld as wild and bizarre creatures; the mirror at their disposal didn't allow them to see anything better or beyond their own reflection. As the trial continued, fearing for its position, which was threatened by the Secretary of State of the Kingdom of Portugal, Sebastião José de Carvalho e Melo, the Marquis of Pombal (1699-1782), the Catholic Church launched an offensive in the

new colony among the natives, with the glorious idea of converting them to Christian doctrine, teaching them the official language of the Crown through the Holy Office. In this, the indigenous ethnic groups, which had already shown themselves to be largely peaceful, even because the men had been eliminated, for the most part, leaving the women, adolescents and girls, were conditioned to obedience and servility, and this they called the development of a Christian spirit.

An interesting paradox in the history of Brazil, involving the Brazilian indigenous people, occurred when the Portuguese Crown, represented by the Marquis of Pombal, expelled the Jesuit priests from Brazilian territory in 1759, leaving the natives to fend for themselves, just as it was before their arrival. Of course, at this time, Rousseau had not yet released his fairy tale exalting the mythological figure, created by him, that of the noble savage; but what is surprising is the fact that, even today, historians consider this moment as a great loss for the nation, because the Indians lost the only means of education they had.

This is a ridiculous idea, because Jesuit education only served to destroy an already existing culture, language, and way of thinking, and implanted others in their place, completely foreign and without any causal connection to the current reality. It introduced diseases that did not exist before, such as the flu and the infamous syphilis, pathologies for which they had no natural defense, much less any medical knowledge. We cannot forget to mention alcohol, which, although there are no anthropological studies that prove the existence of fermented products in indigenous cuisine, is a hypothesis that cannot be discarded before we gain more in-depth knowledge about native life and customs.

The Brazilian indigenous people had legends, warriors, stories, gods, and beautiful women, and all of this was lost amid the construction of an ideological archetype, in which it was defined that they were figures of the most brutal nature, with nothing to offer in terms of culture. The most intriguing thing is that the legends, tales, and exploits of the heroes and heroines narrated in indigenous poetry were authentic constructions, in their entirety, a situation that cannot be affirmed with complete certainty in relation to Western Europeans and all their poetic, literary, and philosophical constructions.

In the case of the Brazilian Indian, the archetype was constructed not through fairy tales, but through the interference of religion, through the action of Anthropology, the media, specialized literature (*sic*) and formal education. The archetype can be used as an element or conceptual basis to understand and explore all types of experiences in which the creative function of the imagination is present, that is, imaginings. Analogical thinking is the way the unconscious operates. This mode is seen in dreams, fantasies, and mythical thinking, precisely

because,

This thinking requires no effort, it moves away from reality into fantasies of the past and future. Here the thought in the form of language ends, image follows image, sensation follows sensation (...) it works effortlessly, spontaneously, with ready-made contents and is guided by unconscious motives (...) it moves away from reality, releases subjective tendencies and is unproductive in relation to adaptation (Jung, 1986, p. 16).

This conception of the archetype serves perfectly what is intended in relation to the indigenous people, because since no one went there to contest what was reported, only creating commissions to *prove* what has been taken as truth since the 16th century about them, everything that was reported about their behavior and personal character proved to be absolute, incontestable truth. In order to transform an ideology into truth, it is not necessary to do away with criticism; it is enough to create in the social imagination an idea that satisfies its belief in the purity of someone who, with this, alleviates the neurotic guilt imposed on everyone by the actions of their ancestors, producing the archetype of the bad individual and the defenseless individual, paying attention to the dichotomy presented through a very well-crafted and consistent discourse, in which the oppressed is not transformed into a passive victim; rather, into someone who is not in adequate conditions to carry out his defense, strategically.

This has been the case throughout Brazilian history, where every mythical Brazilian hero, transformed into an idol, *a posteriori*, has not achieved the level of excellence in his journey because of circumstances, betrayals and conservatism, which insists on maintaining the *status quo* of things as they have always been. It is strange when one hears this thought, because if Brazil were to maintain everything as it has always been in relation to the indigenous people, they would leave them free in their respective living spaces, not wanting to transform them into deputies, ambassadors and other things contrary and strange to their primitive cultures. First, they take care to instill the idea that they are simple creatures, equal in intellect to the feeble-minded and idiots, and cannot be held criminally responsible in any way; but, paradoxically, they can be legislators of a people who are unaware of their legal parameters, interfering in diverse and distinct semantic and cultural fields.

Thus, the archetype of the noble savage attributed to the Brazilian indigenous people and which has taken root, as a truth of excellence, in the nation's thinking can only persist in its existence because of the mediocre critical sense that takes hold of everyone, almost without exception. The inconsistencies are so exaggerated that, no matter how much one tries to understand them, one cannot do so because, by achieving such a feat, it would be an authentic demonstration of passive agreement with an entire scheme of domination and exploitation of a

people that has been going on for centuries and that has no prediction of an end, so that it can once again be considered truly free.

Under the guise of salvation, they destroyed their religion, imposing one on them that had nothing to do with their culture. How did they do this? Well, it was easy! In original cultures where women had to work and their husbands were the ones who received gifts, it was enough to reverse the order and shower them with shiny *gifts* and elegant clothes, as long as they accepted the new faith. This led many young indigenous women to seek holy Christian baptism, so that they could relate to white men and enjoy the same privileges as their sisters.

This idea that the indigenous women were captured with a lasso, as if they were wild animals, is a widespread folkloric imagery that persists in the schizophrenic thinking of the Brazilian population as part of their legends and myths, something very common for the glorification of the pioneering hero. It all starts from the archetypal construction of an individual who, despite being an indomitable and invincible warrior, was tamed and defeated by the most powerful god in human history, Eros, and, once wounded by Anteros' arrow, went out to capture the object of his passion, making her his wife and producing a generation of descendants. This is part of the naturalist romanticism of the 19th century, and cannot be treated as fact, and when reproduced in this way, it creates an illusion of truthfulness that is nothing more than a schizopathic condition, a psychiatric distortion of reality.

Carvalho (1993) speaks of this paradoxical image construction of the hero, the good guy and the villain and, in the case of this work, he is referring to the construction of a personality that never existed and that was constructed for the purpose of maintaining itself in favor of very particular interests and that is still maintained for hidden political interests. It is difficult to find a scientific literary work that explores the indigenous personality from an anthropological point of view, clarifying its behavior as it is, in its entirety, exposing its objectivity and subjectivity. What we have at our disposal are novels that are covered with a veneer of scientificity, labeled by some author who received some title of scientist, writing an imaginary novel in which he describes a people that does not exist with a personological condition, also invented for that purpose: to please the system and always keep the story at a level that serves its particular interests. Oscar Wilde (1854-1900) said that the liar has an impossible mission, that after telling a lie he needs to tell so many others that are capable of supporting the first.

In the case of Brazilian indigenous people, when they produced the archetype of the *noble savage*, a complex problem arose and the maintenance of this ideological construction has been costing the country dearly, which needs to make them creatures increasingly protected from themselves, because with the arrival of globalization through access to the world wide

web, many consumer goods were presented to the indigenous people, as well as the possibility of acquiring them at an affordable price and quickly, the desire to have money and better existential conditions, an existence that was totally different from the one their ancestors lived, gained strength, breaking the infamous bubble that always kept the indigenous people as inferior beings in all aspects, when compared to white people and their technologies.

This is the most interesting point when one proposes to make a comparison between contemporary man and any other people who have a more interesting past history than the ephemeral and paradoxical *Homo sapiens sapiens* who, unlike his ancestors who cannot be forgotten, is forgotten in a matter of days. In all fields of development, much of what we have today in terms of techniques and technologies are mere reproductions, improvements and enhancements of what was already created by the peoples of Antiquity who, ironically, are called simple and backward; understanding, by this, that they did not have technologies (sic).

This situation is fantastic, because it means that, in the same way as the European, whose ancestors are unknown, as if they were abiogenic creatures, produced spontaneously by nature, completely disregarding the entire law of the evolution of species which, as it confronts Hebrew mythology, is still treated as a *theory*, a term that is very far from the etymology and the original semantics of the word, which meant, for the Greeks, *divine revelation*, that is, it was so sublime and powerful that, when a Greek had an idea that clarified a phenomenon on which he was spending his time, he would stop and remain there for hours on end, processing his conclusion.

At the same level is the Brazilian indigenous people, whose ancestors are unknown, where they came from and what happened to them; how the various languages were formed, which, like the rest, are dialects, since *the language* is only Portuguese, European, and everything else is, at most, a sublanguage; in fact, the Jesuit priests were so arrogant that *their language* was only Latin; everything else, including the Portuguese language, could not be treated as such. It is strange that an individual who considers the language of his nation as a sublanguage, suddenly defends the language of peoples subjugated by *forceps* as something to be respected, because it is full of purity, divinity, among other things.

In the end, the archetype they created for the Brazilian indigenous person is nothing more than a caricature devoid of any causal connection with reality, and the result of all this is a lifeless, innocuous character who is manipulated in his tastes and desires by someone who profits from this inertia imposed on him. How the indigenous person can escape from this cage is an impossible task, because every time the State tries to get closer, it is rejected by some humanitarian group (sic) that is always fighting for the sovereignty of the original peoples; but, paradoxically, the same warriors of originality are there using state-of-the-art communication

devices, designer clothes, digital time markers and other modern gadgets.

An exhausting condition of contemporary times is the pathological need to be seen; which has become a condition of recognition based on virtual visualizations and, until the time when indigenous people lived secluded in their villages, far from the so-called modern mechanisms of social interaction, in which this sounds more like a euphemism, because participation always occurs [*or most of the time*] remotely and virtually, their entire life was based on participating in meetings and worship, presenting their ideas pertinent to everyday problems. However, with the globalization process that has taken over human thought, it is more common for individuals to create channels on the network and talk about what they find interesting, and whoever, on the other side, through anonymity, wants something that they believe has some value, watches and makes comments, becoming or not a follower of that content producer, something as if the network were, from then on, a *self-service restaurant*, where instead of food, content that someone considers to be of an intellectual nature is available. However, the archetypal image produced and crystallized in the popular imagination that the indigenous person is an innocent figure without scientific culture persists, because research is carried out on them and not with them. Added to this is the condition that their methods and habits of life are considered simplistic, in contrast to the scientific development that modern society is experiencing. Thus, the connection of these people with modernity, in itself, is not enough to break with the infamous paradigm created around them regarding cognitive and intellectual aspects.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The archetypal representations and values of the collective unconscious remain involuntarily alive, both intrinsically and extrinsically, and even though contemporary Indians have lost their cultural values through globalization and the technological revolution that has caused behavioral changes across the planet, it would not be any different in indigenous communities, precisely because in an attempt to protect them and their culture from the influence of white men, the latter ends up influencing them to consume the culture they wish to resist. This may seem like an incomprehensible paradox; however, contact with technology generates curiosity and a desire to experiment, a natural feeling in any human being, regardless of their origin or culture.

Through research, it is noted that mass media have driven indigenous communities to lose their cultural values; however, the collective unconscious is preserved in the indigenous

identity in a subjective way, at the same time that, paradoxically, the image of the noble savage is consolidated in the Brazilian unconscious, using an archetypal model already universalized in the popular imagination. This represents the most interesting paradox in contemporary history, in which, while the object and its entire psychology are transformed, the perception of it, instilled in the popular imagination, remains unchanged, which can be explained by the way in which the media takes care to protect one from everyone's view and present to others the image that interests them.

The interpretation that is projected onto the psychology of the object, in this case, is controversial in itself, because it is based on information that is produced and disseminated for ideological purposes of maintaining a vision created many centuries ago, as if the full impact of technological development and national thought could not affect indigenous people. Social indignation is evident when Brazilian aborigines present themselves using modern cars and communication devices, using machines for planting and harvesting, as if they were obliged to persist in their traditional methods.

This reveals that the archetype formed in Brazilian thinking about indigenous peoples has become a sacred condition and that its destruction represents a blasphemy against that which was created with so much love and care by the Jesuit priests, back in the 16th century. This sounds ridiculous, because the world has changed and along with it, the laws, especially the one that places indigenous peoples in the same condition as all Brazilian citizens, enjoying the same rights and duties. Thus, the astonishment that they desire existential conditions different from those represented by their original culture is an affront to the dignity of the human person, a concept dear to the Federal Constitution of 1988.

REFERENCES

CARVALHO, JM *The Formation of Souls: The Imaginary of the Republic in Brazil*. New York: Routledge, 1993.

DURAND, G. *The Symbolic Imagination*. São Paulo: Cultrix and EDUSP, 1998.

HILLMAN, J. *Archetypal Psychology*. São Paulo: Cultrix, 1992.

JUNG, CG *Symbols of transformation*. Petrópolis: Vozes, 1986. (Originally published in 1924).

SERBENA, CA considerations on the unconscious: myth, symbol and archetype in analytical psychology. *Journal of the Gestalt Approach* – XVI(1): 76-82, Jan-Jul, 2010.